

Cyanobacterial Blooms on the Indian Coast: A Review on Causes, Effects and Trends

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Key Points:

- Coastal ecosystems are vulnerable to toxic cyanobacterial blooms.
- *Trichodesmium erythraeum* is the common bloom-forming Cyanobacteria in Indian coastal waters.
- Monsoonal effects, Discharge from rivers, seasonal upwelling and nutrient pollution are the driving force.

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Abstract

The Coastal ecosystems play a significant role in social, economic, and cultural aspects of human life. Cyanobacterial blooms have direct and indirect effects on the main sectors, including public health, commerce, fisheries, tourism, and recreational activities. In India, one-third of the population depends on marine resources for their living. Indian coastal regions have diverse ecosystems, including mangrove swamps, brackish water lakes, and coral reefs. Cyanobacterial blooms in Indian coastal waters are influenced by monsoonal effects, discharge from rivers, seasonal upwelling, and nutrient pollution. *Trichodesmium erythraeum* is the most common bloom-forming species in coastal regions of India. A total of 154 microalgal blooms occurred in the peninsular regions of India between 1908 and 2017. *Trichodesmium* accounted for 31.8% of the total blooms. The Arabian Sea is more prone to *Trichodesmium* blooms due to warm water, intense upwelling, and higher salinity. The current review paper deals with past events and future possibilities for the formation of cyanobacterial blooms along the coastal regions of India, considering changing climatic conditions and anthropogenic eutrophication.

Keywords: Water, Pollution, Bacteria, Toxins, Algal bloom.

1. Introduction

Cyanobacteria are photosynthetic prokaryotic organisms with a wide range of applications in medicine, food, cosmetics, and agriculture. Their ability to withstand extreme conditions such as ultraviolet radiation, drought, low light, and high salt concentration makes survival in various habitats easy. They can be found in terrestrial to aquatic ecosystems, surface water to deep oceans, fresh water to saline water (Aparicio-Muriana et al., 2023; Haque et al., 2017; Hinojosa et al., 2019; Tan and Phyto, 2020). Over the last decade, 50 new genera of Cyanobacteria were identified apart from the more than 2000 known species (Andreeva et al., 2020). Availability of nutrients, surface water temperature, and water stratification, along with other factors, induces cyanobacteria colonization in fresh, marine,

and brackish water; this massive growth of cyanobacteria is called “bloom”. The increased visibility of surface cyanobacteria causes a reduction in sunlight penetration, depletion of oxygen, and enrichment of nutrients. Over time, the blooms start to collapse, leading to the deposition of large amounts of organic matter. Eventually, it creates a hypoxia condition or “dead zone” which can cause the mortality of aquatic organisms (Paerl and Otten, 2013; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2019). The absence of Cyanobacteria in the marine environment possibly indicates conditionally cleaner marine bottom sediment (Andreeva et al., 2020).

Cyanobacteria species found in marine environments can be divided into freely floating Planktonic cyanobacteria and Benthic Cyanobacteria. Prochlorococcus, Synechocytic, Synechococcus, Cynobium, Oscillatoriales, Nostocales,

Chroococcales, and Synechococcales are some of the commonly found cyanobacteria in the marine environment (Dufresne et al., 2008; Flombaum et al., 2013; Perera et al., 2023; Tan and Phyto, 2020). Benthic cyanobacteria growing on corals often produce toxins (cyanotoxins) that may enter into fish and mollusks that feed on coral reefs. Benthic cyanobacteria have a unique gliding motility when in contact with solid soil, sediments, and rocks (Perera et al., 2023). Some of the most common toxin-producing cyanobacteria that may flourish in both fresh and marine waters include *Anabaena*, *Aphanizomenon*, *Cylindrospermopsis*, *Lyngbya*, *Nodularia*, *Oscillatoria*, *Trichodesmium*, *Microcystis*, *Planktothrix* (Paerl and Otten, 2013). *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon* dominate inshore cyanobacterial bloom at low salinity regions worldwide (Sellner, 1997).

Cyanotoxin is a secondary metabolite produced by Cyanobacteria that has been illustrious over the past 3 decades for its toxic effects on varieties of live forms (Svirčev et al., 2022). The mechanisms of production of secondary metabolite by cyanobacteria are still a mystery (Aparicio-Muriana et al., 2023). In addition to cyanotoxins, more than 2000 secondary metabolites have been identified from cyanobacteria that have antioxidant, photoprotective and moisturizing allelopathic properties (Perera et al., 2023).

More than 2000 secondary metabolites have been identified from cyanobacteria other than cyanotoxins; having antioxidant, photoprotective, moisturizing allelopathic properties and have applications in human health, biofuel, cosmetics, and bioremediation (Perera et al., 2023). As per WHO, cyanotoxins are considered the emerging public health issue that is likely to cause health problems in humans and aquatic organisms. Based on their toxicological effects, these secondary metabolites can be classified into non-toxic secondary metabolites and toxic secondary metabolites. Phytohormones, siderophores, and UV protective compounds fall under Non-toxic secondary metabolites. Toxic secondary metabolites can be classified based on their toxicological targets as Hepatotoxins, Neurotoxins, Cytotoxins, and Dermatotoxins (Haque et al., 2017; Hinojosa et al., 2019). The main cyanotoxins include Microcystin (MC), Nodularin (NOD), cylindrospermopsin (CYN), Anatoxin (ATX), Guanitoxin (GNTX), Saxitoxin (STX) and Lyngbyatoxin (LTX) groups (Svirčev et al.,

2022). The effects of toxins depend on the route of exposure, concentration, and biochemical activities (Tatters et al., 2019). The presence of other chemicals in the water can produce synergic effects along with cyanotoxins in exposed organisms. IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae listed 37 species of Cyanobacteria as toxin-producing (Shaika et al., 2023). Except for Microcystin-LR (MC-LR,) here is no guideline value for any cyanotoxins in seafood (Abdallah et al., 2021).

In the world, coastal ecosystems are the most productive and vulnerable ecosystems. Beyond the scope of fishing, trading, and commerce, coastal regions regulate and store nutrients, remove pollutants, and prevent erosion and storms (Nayak, 2017). The growth of cyanobacteria in the coastal environment is controlled by factors such as vertical mixing, light, salinity, organic matter content, and rain-water runoff. The 7500 km stretch of the Indian coastal line contains varieties of ecosystems, including mangrove swamps, brackish water lakes, and coral reefs, inland and offshore along the two important seas, Arabian Sea (west) and Bay of Bengal (east) waters (D'Silva et al., 2012; Nayak, 2017; Paerl and Otten, 2013). The percentage of factories situated in the coastal region (68%) reveals the importance of coastal regions in India's trade and economy. The toxins produced by the Cyanobacterial blooms can bioaccumulate and eventually enter into the human diet. Frequent blooms in the coastal environment may lead to the loss of fish and shellfish, which impacts the economy of the nation. Climate change and nutrient pollution are acting as a catalyst for the formation of blooms in the coastal environment. This paper deals with the possibilities for the formation of Cyanobacterial blooms along the coasts of India, as well as past events and the latest trends in climatic conditions and nutrient pollution.

2. Background

The first appearance of *Trichodesmium* bloom along with *Noctiluca scintillans* made in 1908 in the Arabian Sea along the Indian coastal line led to the massive killing of fish (Chatziefthimiou et al., 2021; Haridevi et al., 2022). Around the world, the presence of harmful cyanobacterial bloom were reported in varieties of ecosystems. In the Baltic Sea, cyanobacterial blooms are a common scenario dominated by the species *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* and *Nodularia spumigena* (Kanoschina et al., 2003) due to the in-

creased nutrient level in the sea water (Mazur-Marzec and Plinski, 2009). In tropical oceans, Trichodesmium groups are the main contributors to planktonic blooms (Golubic et al., 2010), and the common tropical cyanobacteria *Lyngbya majuscula* produces the highest number of toxins that can cause discomfort to the skin and eye (Andreeva et al., 2020). The toxins associated with *L. majuscula* include Lyngbyatoxin-A (LTA), and debromoaplysiatoxin (DTA), which can cause asthma-like symptoms and severe dermatitis in humans (O'Neil et al., 2012)(O'Neil et al., 2012).

The presence of cyanotoxins MCs, CYNs, STXs, NODs, and ATXs are reported in Europe, North America, South America, Australia, Asia, and South Africa in varieties of ecosystems even though the distribution and diversity are uneven (Kulabhusan and Campbell, 2021). In the early 90s, in the aquaculture sites on the coast of Canada, hepatotoxins in the marine environment caused severe liver disease in Atlantic Salmon (Camacho-Muñoz et al., 2021). The first report on the death of marine mammals due to cyanotoxins microcystin was reported by Miller et al. (2010). Since the 19th century, massive blooms of cyanobacteria in the summer season have been reported in the Baltic Sea (Bianchi et al., 2000). In the northern Baltic Sea, summer blooms of *Nodularia Spumigena* caused accumulation of Nodularin in mussels and clams up to 1490 µg/kg dw and 130 µg/kg dw, respectively (Rattner et al., 2022). Similarly, the presence of Nodularin was identified in all the collected samples of bivalve from the coast of Bohuslän in 2020-2022 during cyanobacterial bloom on the coast of Sweden. The concentration of Nodularin ranged from 7- 397 µg/kg (España Amórtégui et al., 2023). A state of emergency was declared in Florida in 2016 due to the transport of microcystic cells from Lake Okeechobee that caused blooms at the mouth of Caloosahatchee and St. Luice Rivers into the coastal water of the Gulf of Mexico (Howard et al., 2023; Metcalf et al., 2021). There are also reports that net pen liver disease in salmon pens in Washington and British Columbia is caused by microcystin-related compounds (Sellner, 1997). The largest estuarine cyanobacterial bloom in South America occurred in the summer of 2019 in the coastal zone of Uruguayan, which affected all the beaches along the estuary and persisted for four months (Kruk et al., 2021). Other than fishes and crustaceans, toxic blooms can also affect water birds. The presence of Saxitoxins and microcystins was identified from the tissue and stomach content of Dalmatian Pelicans died during the massive water bird die-off

that occurred at the Karla reservoir in Greece (Rattner et al., 2022).

3. Factors facilitating the formation of cyanobacterial blooms in the coastal environments

3.1. Nutrients

The sources of nutrients in coastal environments may include agricultural runoff, excess animal feed, animal waste, storm runoff, and wastewater treatment effluent (Figure 1) (Aparicio-Muriana et al., 2023; Tatters et al., 2019). Studies show that relatively higher toxicity of many cyanobacteria species is seen when nitrogen (N) is in stoichiometrically excess over Phosphorus (P); having special reference to microcystin (Heisler et al., 2008). Many genera, including Aphanizomenon, Cyndrospermopsis, and Lyngbya can fix atmospheric nitrogen using other available nutrients (Paerl and Otten, 2013; Sanseverino et al., 2016). This acts as a supplementary source of N, even though it can not meet the level of required Nitrogen (Paerl and Otten, 2013). Trichodesmium is nitrogen-fixing cyanobacteria likely to be a major contributor to the total nitrogen cycle and reported throughout the Atlantic, Pacific, Indian Ocean, Caribbean, and South China Sea (Capone et al., 1997). In the Baltic Sea, heterocystous species of cyanobacteria act as an additional supplier of nitrogen to the sea (Mazur-Marzec and Plinski, 2009). Cyanobacteria act as the source of food and Nitrogen for the coral reef environment (Andreeva et al., 2020). In addition to nitrogen fixation, Cyanobacteria have storage capacity for P (both mineral and organic) and can sequester iron and other trace metals (Andreeva et al., 2020; Sanseverino et al., 2016). In the ocean, iron acts as an active part in the breaking down of nitrite, nitrate, and nitrogen gas and blooms faster in the iron-rich environment. A higher concentration of Fe leads to less dependence of Phytoplankton on sea surface temperature for blooms (Singh and Kumar, 2021). The response towards nutrient concentration and temperature of cyanobacteria is species-specific (Huisman et al., 2018). Coral reef flats can act as a barrier that prevents the mixing of lagoon water with open ocean and increases the residence time of nutrients in water (Soondur et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Factors influencing the formation of Cyanobacterial blooms in the marine environment.

3.2. Precipitation pattern

The precipitation pattern also influences the magnitude and timing of the nutrient pulse. Extreme rainfall may lead to the discharge of nutrients from large surfaces and groundwater into waterbodies (Paerl and Otten, 2013). Flood and heavy rainfall may also carry invasive freshwater cyanobacteria to the coastal environments (Preece et al., 2017). The foremost toxic bloom of Microcystin aeruginosa in the Swan River estuary of Western Australia formed in January 2000 after the unusual summer rain. The freshwater filled on the surface of the estuary due to the rainfall triggered the growth of the cyanobacterial bloom with a cell density of 1 million cells per mL, eventually leading to the closing of the estuary for ten days from recreational activity and fishing (Robson and Hamilton, 2003). Dry periods cause water evaporation, leading to a concentration of nutrients, an increase in water temperature, and an increase in the area of still water, which accelerates cyanobacteria growth (Sanseverino et al., 2016). The findings of Soon-dur et al. (2022), indicate the rainfall-induced nutrient load to the southwestern Indian Ocean around Mauritius island led to the increase in the micro phytoplankton mass, but a contradictory drift was seen in the case of Cyanobacteria. Mahanadi estuary on the east coast of India experiences a

higher number of cyanobacteria during the post-monsoon season which can be due to the observed higher concentration of nutrients compared to other seasons (Naik et al., 2009); the summer monsoonal winds are capable of bringing nutrient rich deeper water to surface (Glibert and Burford, 2017).

3.3. Transportation from freshwater to the marine environment

Cyanotoxins are produced in the inland waterbodies that can be transported downstream and reach coastal regions. Miller et al. (2010) first reported that microcystin from land pollutes the marine environment. The unexplained mammal death in the Central California coastal line led the way to the discovery of the transportation of cyanotoxins from freshwater to marine water (Tatters et al., 2019). The estuaries face a dual risk of impacts from the blooms originating in coastal oceans as well as inland waters (Howard et al., 2023). One of the potential risks faced by the public and the environment in the states of the US is the transport of toxic cyanotoxins from freshwater to marine water (Anderson et al., 2021). Due to the absence of integrated monitoring, the range of environmental issues related to the transport of cyanotoxins to downstream receiving waters is

uncertain (Howard et al., 2023). These blooms can travel kilometres in the down streams before reaching the coast, as the scum reached at Uruguay coast after traveling 100km for two weeks from the entrance of the Uruguay River to the RdIP estuary (Kruk et al., 2021).

3.4. Temperature

Increasing sea surface temperature intensifies the chances for the formation of cyanobacterial blooms since they are adapted to elevate temperature. Their ability to absorb light energy locally increases the sea surface temperature and leads to spatially and temporally expanding the bloom (Fu et al., 2012). Planktonic bloom-forming Cyanobacteria attain maximum growth at elevated temperatures, often over 250C (D'Silva et al., 2012; Huisman et al., 2018). Stratification of the seawater can be accelerated by the effects of global increase in the temperature and freshening of seawater (Fu et al., 2012). Climate change induced stratification may start earlier in the spring and continue till the fall. Sea Surface Temperature reported during the *Trichodesmium erythraeum* bloom in the Andaman Sea was 27- 32°C (Kumar et al., 2015).

3.5. Salinity

In the case of salinity, some species can tolerate salinity up to 15 ppm, like *Anabaena* and *Anabaenopsis* and other species, like *Nodularia Spumigena* can withstand salinities over 20 ppm (Paerl and Otten, 2013). Studies have shown that *Microcystin aeruginosa* can survive at a salinity of 0.1 to 18 for a long period and can release intracellular microcystin in higher salinity waters (Howard et al., 2023; Preece et al., 2017). *Anabaena*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Microcystin*, and *Oscillatoria* are some of the species that may show fast growth in saline habitats (Preece et al., 2017). Survey conducted on the saltpan regions of the Southwest coastal regions of Tamil Nadu showed the diversity of Cyanobacteria in extreme saline regions (Sugumar et al., 2011), where 18 species of cyanobacteria, including *Oscillatoria*, *Lyngbya*, *Microcystis*, *Spirulina*, *Chroococcus*, and *Calothrix* genera were identified.

3.6. Atmospheric CO₂

The increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentration can stimulate surface lodging cyanobacteria, they utilize CO₂ as their

source of Carbon (Andreeva et al., 2020). Due to the difference in the uptake of CO₂ and bicarbonate bloom-forming cyanobacteria exhibit diverse CO₂ responses (Visser et al., 2016). Microcystin favors low concentrations of dissolved CO₂ because of its high-affinity bicarbonate uptake system (Huisman et al., 2018). *Trichodesmium* shows increased nitrogen fixation and growth under increasing CO₂ partial pressure. The rising global CO₂ level can increase the frequency of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* blooms in saline habitats (Shetye et al., 2013).

4. Indian Coast

As per the 2011 census, 2661 towns and 3827 villages are situated in the coastal regions of India, which means more than half of the total cities in India. A total of one-third of the population of India lives in the coastal region, comprising 9 states and 66 districts. The east and west coasts of India are diverse in many aspects. East coast is a flat terrain containing beaches, coral reefs, back waters, lakes and Saltpan. In contrast, west coast is a narrow rolling plain containing estuaries and a few sandy beaches. Several sites in Indian coastal regions, increased nutrient outflow to coastal water is seen due to the increase in population and agricultural practices (Senapati and Gupta, 2014).

The Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal have received $0.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3$ and $1.6 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3$ fresh water from rivers, respectively (D'Silva et al., 2012). Rivers like Ganga and Brahmaputra are the most significant suppliers of nutrients to the Bay of Bengal. Due to the high availability of carbonate, the Bay of Bengal has the highest transport efficiency of nutrients. Freshwater inflow directly influences the enrichment of the Bay of Bengal. This region meets 6% of the world's fish demand. The increasing need for dietary demand due to the population explosion accelerated the use of fertilizers in agriculture. P fertilizers have had an 18-fold increase in global use since 1940 (Wurtsbaugh et al., 2019), whereas N fertilizers have seen a nine-fold increase over the past forty years. Since only up to half of the applied N fertilizer is being taken up by crops, the rest is lost via ammonia volatilization, denitrification, runoff, leaching, or accumulated in soil (Aparicio-Muriana et al., 2023). The use of fertilizers across the floodplains due to the increasing demand for food possibly has a role in the enrichment of the Bay of Bengal (Bala Krishna Prasad, 2012; Singh and Kumar, 2021). The influence of monsoons is most ap-

Figure 2: Map showing the locations at which Cyanobacterial blooms reported along the coast regions of India.

parent in the Bay of Bengal (Preethi Latha et al., 2014). According to Bandyopadhyay and Biswas (2021), it is predicted that the Bay of Bengal will be 90% more eutrophic in the future. Variables such as pH, temperature, salinity, nitrate, phosphate, and chlorophyll-a positively correlated with the phytoplankton composition in the Arabian Sea (Rai and Rajashekhar, 2014). N fixation is a source of nutrients in the Arabian Sea compared to the Bay of Bengal and has less productivity than the Arabian Sea (Shetye et al., 2013).

4.1. Vulnerability of Indian coastal regions

Most of the blooms on the Indian coasts are influenced by factors such as monsoonal effects, discharges from rivers, and seasonal upwellings (D’Silva et al., 2012). Water surface warming facilitates conditions for the growth of buoyant cyanobacteria due to stable water stratification and less vertical mixing (Huisman et al., 2018). From the coastal waters of India, 240 species of Cyanobacteria of 50 genera were recorded (Andreeva et al., 2020). As

per the study of Oyeku and Mandal (2021), from 1908 to 2017, a total of 154 marine microalgal blooms occurred around the peninsular region of India. Among these *Trichodesmium* contributed 31.8% of the total blooms. *Trichodesmium erythraeum* is the most commonly found species of *Trichodesmium*, and its presence was detected in various coastal areas of India, including the Arabian Sea, Bay of Bengal, and Cochin backwaters. D’Silva et al. (2012) reviewed the frequency and occurrence of algal blooms along the coasts of India from 1908 to 2009. Blooms of *T.erythraeum*, *T.thiebautii*, *T. hildebrontii*, and *M.aerginosa* have occurred 25 times along the east and west coast of India, causing effects including mortality of marine fishes and shellfish. According to Padmakumar et al. (2012) a total of 80 algal blooms were recorded in Indian waters between 1998 and 2010, out of which 27 were by cyanobacteria. In recent years, cyanobacteria blooms have been reported along different coastal regions of India (Dias et al., 2020; Ramesh et al., 2021; Shunmugam et al., 2017). It is evident that cyanobacterial blooms are a common scenario in Indian waters (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Table 1: List of Cyanobacterial blooms along the west and east coast of India in the chronological order.

Causative Organ-ism	Year	Season	Location	Characteristics	Reference
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	1968 April	Spring Inter Monsoon	Laccadives	Bare minimum nitrate-N	Qasim, 1970
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	1972 March	Summer	Arabian Sea, Central part of west coast	Lasted for 9 days, 5-7 meters in width and extended to sev- eral miles, Color - day light grey with some dark patches	Ramamurthy et al., 1972
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	1973 March	Summer	Cochin, Ara- bian Sea	Over a stretch more than 40 miles	Sakthivel and Hari- das, 1974
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i> and <i>Trichodesmium thiebautii</i>	1975 May	Spring Inter monsoon	Goa	Between the depth 10- 20 m depth zone	Pant and Devassy, 1976
<i>Trichodesmium</i>	1977 March	Summer	South-west coast of India	Ammonia-N and low levels of other nutri- ents	Verlecar, 1978
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2001 April	Summer	East coast	Undisturbed patches with brownish yellow color	Retnamma et al., 2003
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2001 April	Summer	Open waters of Bay of Ben- gal, Karaikal, and south of Calcutta	Very low NO ₃ – N concentration	Retnamma et al., 2003

Causative Organ-ism	Year	Season	Location	Characteristics	Reference
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2005 May	Summer	Southwest coast of India	A colony consisted of 3.6×10^5 cells, with a depth of about 47 m, covering an area of 7 km in length and 2 km width	Krishnan et al., 2007
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2007 March	Summer	East coast of Kalpakkam	High Concentration of Ammonia, Total Nitrogen, and Phosphate. No fish mortalities and other organisms occurred.	Satpathy et al., 2021
<i>Trichodesmium</i>	2007 April	Spring inter monsoon	Eastern Arabian Sea off Goa	High concentration of CHCl_3 and CCl_4 in surface layer.	Roy et al., 2017
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i> and <i>Trichodesmium thiebautii</i>	2008 April	Spring inter monsoon	Eastern Arabian Sea	Cell concentrations recorded as 3.05×10^6 trichomes L^{-1}	Basu et al., 2011
<i>Trichodesmium</i>	2008		Kalpakkam	10-20 cm patches about several km along	Khot et al., 2018
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i> and <i>Trichodesmium thiebautii</i>	2009 June	Summer monsoon	South-eastern Arabian Sea	Pale brown to pinkish, No fish mortalities were observed	Padmakumar et al., 2010
<i>Trichodesmium</i>	2010	Inter monsoon bloom	Kumbla	SST 29-30°C, Salinity < 35 PSU	Raghavan et al., 2010
<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i>	2012 June	Monsoon	Muttukadu Back waters, South-east coast of India	Severe fish mass mortality	Prasath et al., 2014

Causative Organ-ism	Year	Season	Location	Characteristics	Reference
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2013	Winter sea-son	Jaitapur coast of Maharashtra, India	Massive bloom	Khot et al., 2018
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2013 March	Summer	Andaman coast near Phoenix Bay jetty, Port Blair	Cytotoxicity in cell line HepG2 and HaCat and caused DNA damage in lymphocytes in Vitro.	Narayana et al., 2014
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2013 April	Spring Inter monsoon	Andaman Sea	SST 27-32°C, Salinity 32.4-34 PSU. The hooking rate of fish ranged from 0-0.32%.	Kumar et al., 2015
Trichodesmium	2014-18	Spring Inter monsoon	Coastal waters of Goa	Large patches. SST ranged between 30.8 °C and 31.8 °C. Salinity varied from 35-36 PSU.	Dias et al., 2020
Trichodesmium	2015 August		Gulf of Mannar, Tamil Nadu	First report of multi-class neurotoxic producing Trichodesmium bloom	Shunmugam et al., 2017
<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i>	2019 April		Mandapam group of islands, Southeast coast of India, Tamil Nadu	No indication of mortalities of fish	Ramesh et al., 2021
<i>Synechococcus</i>	2019 April		Kundukal Jetty, Mandapam region, Southeast coast of Tamil Nadu		Ramesh et al., 2021

During the post-northeastern monsoon, intense *Trichodesmium erythraeum* bloom occurs on India's southeast coast (Mohanty et al., 2010). Along the east and west coast of India, cases of mortality were reported caused by the trichodesmium blooms (Shunmugam et al., 2017). Fish mortalities reported in the coastal waters of Tamilnadu were due to the massive blooms of Trichodesmium (D'Silva et al., 2012). Trichodesmium blooms are commonly known as Sea sawdust for their sporadic appearance (Dias et al., 2020). Trichodesmium blooms can fix a large amount of atmospheric Nitrogen and also act as a rich source of organic matter in the coastal waters (Dias et al., 2020) In 2008, *T. erythraeum* caused 10-20 cm patches that spanned several km along the coastal water of Kalpakkam. Massive bloom of *T. erythraeum* was reported during the winter season in 2013 on the Jaitapur coast of Maharashtra (Khot et al., 2018). During spring, inter monsoon bloom of the trichodesmium is common in the coastal waters of Goa (Dias et al., 2020). In the Arabian Sea, trichodesmium blooms occur annually, and their study revealed an increase in the frequency of occurrence (Padmakumar et al., 2012). Other than this, during the bloom of Trichodesmium bloom, high concentrations of Ammonia were reported during the 2009 bloom of trichodesmium in the coastal waters of southeast India (Mohanty et al., 2010).

Microcystin aeruginosa bloom reported in the Muttukadu backwaters of the Southeast coast of India caused severe mortality of fishes due to the toxin exerted by the bloom (Prasath et al., 2014). Consumption of bloom affected mussels, resulted in the hospitalization of 85 people and the death of 3 due to paralytic shellfish poisoning in 1981. Similar case was reported in Kerala during September 1997, resulting in the death of 7 persons and hospitalization of over 500 (Bhat and Matondkar, 2004). Gut analysis results of fishes collected from Kollam, Kochin and Kannur during the trichodesmium blooms in 2009 showed that trichodesmium forms 55-65% of the total stomach content even though there are no fish mortalities were reported (Padmakumar et al., 2010). Toxicity study on the dense bloom of Trichodesmium that occurred in the Phoenix Bay of Andaman in 2013 showed cytotoxicity in cell lines HepGe2 and HaCat and caused DNA damage in human lymphocytes in vitro (Narayana et al., 2014).

Factors such as warmer water, intense upwelling, and higher salinity in the Arabian Sea favor the increase in

the number of occurrences of Trichodesmium blooms and there is an increase in the frequency and intensity of *Trichodesmium blooms in the Arabian Sea* (Manuri et al., 2023). The baseline study of data from 1992-2015 indicates an increase in the temperature, Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, Dissolve Inorganic Phosphorus, Phytoplankton, and zooplankton along the Indian coast (Manuri et al., 2023). According to scientific studies, changes in the average temperature, precipitation pattern, and monsoon timing will affect the India's sea-levels and biodiversity. Since 1950, along the coasts of India there is a 2.5 mm rise in the sea level per year (Senapati and Gupta, 2014). Sea level rise may result in the submergence of coastal areas and salt water intrusion into the coastal area, facilitating the growth of marine cyanobacteria in the coastal environment. Nutrient runoff into the coastal areas can increase by extreme climatic events. The chances of extreme rainfall and flooding events are likely to increase globally in the near future (Lincoln et al., 2023). Riverine discharge, mixing of surface ocean due to wind, eddy pumping, coastal upwellings, and ocean currents are the major source of nutrients in the Bay of Bengal and also reversing monsoonal winds have a significant role in the regulation of biogeochemical cycles (Chinnadurai et al., 2021). Meso scale warm core eddies are common in Bay of Bengal which induce vertical mixing of nutrients (Chinnadurai et al., 2021; Sellner, 1997). Warm core eddies facilitate the growth of Trichodemium instead of diatoms and dianoflagellates (Chinnadurai et al., 2021).

4.2. Economic Viability

Since India is a developing country, the importance of coastal regions in the economy of the country is undebatable. Reoccurring Cyanobacterial blooms may have direct and indirect effects on the socio-economy of the country. The main sectors include public health, commerce, fisheries, tourism, and recreational activities. Monitoring and management activities imply a greater burden on the country's economy. As a developing country, in which 3.5M people rely on coastal ecosystems for living, it is important to monitor the occurrence of harmful blooms in the coastal ecosystems of the country. 42% of the total area of India includes 66 coastal districts and 6 coastal states, with 17% of the total population. More than 70 cities including Kochi, Mumbai, Kolkata, and Chennai are situated along the coastal region of India (Senapati and Gupta, 2014). About 3.5 to 4.0 million tonnes of marine fish are har-

vested in India each year (Nayak, 2017). Globally, a major part of the human diet comprises seafood. Cyanotoxins produced in the marine environment cause potential risks due to exposure to fishes, mollusks, shellfish, and marine mammals, causing challenges to marine resources and human health. Countries in the Middle-East-North African regions use marine water from the Arabian Sea as the major source of water for desalination to meet the water demand (Chatziefthimiou et al., 2021).

Detached scum of benthic cyanobacteria can cause economic and health issues when they reach the shore. It causes additional expenses for cleaning the mess, which can potentially cause health issues (O'Neil et al., 2012).

5. Research gap

Studies on the occurrence and/or impacts of harmful algal blooms in the coastal environment (marine environment) indicate the presence of cyanobacterial blooms worldwide. The lack of research on the occurrence of harmful cyanobacterial blooms on the coasts of India limits the better understanding of their frequent occurrence and knowledge of the mitigation strategies. More studies are required to understand the frequency and intensity of the occurrence of harmful cyanobacterial bloom.

6. Conclusion

Since 40% of the total world population lives within 100 km of the coastal line, it is undeniable to study the effects of cyanobacterial blooms within the coastal area. Coastal pollution, nutrient outflow, and extreme climatic events are triggering the frequency of formation of cyanobacterial blooms in the coastal regions of India. Changes in the precipitation pattern may also cause dilution of salt water on the surface and facilitate the growth of freshwater cyanobacteria. Studies on the trends in climatic conditions and nutrient pollution expose the chances of the increase of events related to the harmful cyanobacterial blooms on the coasts of India (east and west). The present review observed less number of studies on Cyanobacterial blooms. There should be studies on frequency and intensity of the cyanobacterial blooms and its impacts.

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Author Contributions

Swathy Soman- Literature collection, Draft preparations
Mahesh Mohan- Conceptualization, Interpretation, Corrections

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there are no known competing interests.

Data Availability Statement

No data sets were generated or analyzed during the study.

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